

Artificial Intelligence in Educational Administration: Opportunities, Challenges, and Ethics

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Abstract

This article aims to examine the impact of the rapid development of artificial intelligence technologies on educational management, the opportunities offered by AI tools, and the challenges they bring. The research will examine the place of AI in educational management, its advantages and disadvantages in light of studies in the literature, and will address them within ethical frameworks. Studies show that AI technologies enable faster execution of routine tasks and processes, healthier decision-making processes, and support personalized learning management. These topics are also closely related to the field of educational management. However, it also carries risks such as ensuring data security, carrying algorithmic biases, and weakening human interaction. It is an undeniable fact that it has become a necessity for managers and leaders working in the education sector to develop themselves with "next-generation leadership" competencies in this dilemma and to follow the reflections of artificial intelligence in the education sector.

Keywords: Educational administration, AI, Ethics, Education transformation

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Introduction

Technology and education have a long history of partnership. However, this partnership has grown even stronger during the COVID-19 pandemic. Everyone involved in education was forced to spend a significant amount of time with screens and technology. While families had previously imposed limits on cell phone and tablet use, the pandemic left them with no choice but to encourage their use (Özer, 2025). When the literature on artificial intelligence (AI) is examined, it can be stated that the concept's initial starting point began with the search for an answer to the question "Can a machine think?" asked by Alan Turing in his Mind paper in the 1950s (Varol, 2025). In recent years, with the dizzying speed of technological change, artificial intelligence has shown its effect in all areas of industry. This effect has also influenced the perspective of educational institutions on training well-equipped and qualified personnel (Bayındır, 2023). With the rapid winds of digital transformation, artificial intelligence has begun to attract attention in terms of the administrative and academic processes of educational institutions (Polat, 2024).

Academic articles researching developments in the field of artificial intelligence in education reveal that there are fewer findings from before 2020. The findings indicate that research was scarce between 2010 and 2015, that comprehensive research on this topic began between 2016 and 2019, and that a large portion of the literature was enriched after 2018. Most studies have focused on the challenges of transitioning to artificial intelligence in education. However, opportunities and benefits are also discussed (Tahiru, 2021). Nevertheless, artificial intelligence has been discussed and researched much more in recent years. Although artificial intelligence is a rapidly developing technology today, the ability of people, especially educators, to recognize and use artificial intelligence is not progressing at the same pace. Therefore, it can be said that educators working at all levels of education are in a common observation and learning process on this issue. Artificial intelligence awareness is related to understanding the logic of this new technology and using it correctly. Therefore, it is

normal for there to be differences in artificial intelligence awareness and use among educators and administrators at different levels of educational institutions, in different types of schools, and in different locations (Şimşek, 2025).

Artificial intelligence supports administrators in fundamental areas such as analysing big data, planning, decision-making, and resource management (Bayraktar, 2023; Polat and Hakan, 2025). As in other fields, artificial intelligence appears as an advanced technology that improves and develops management processes such as planning, organization, and decision-making in the field of educational administration. This technology automates routine administrative tasks, analyses complex data, and helps administrators make faster decisions, but it also brings with it a number of technical and ethical problems (Igbokwe, 2023; Jose, 2025).

Methodology

This study was prepared using a qualitative research design and document analysis (documentary review) method. National and international academic studies examining the opportunities arising from the development of artificial intelligence within an ethical framework were reviewed to identify current trends on the subject. As a result of these trends, the opportunities and challenges presented by artificial intelligence technologies in the field of educational management were systematically addressed. In addition, proposed solution approaches for the ethical problems experienced in this process were also discussed and briefly summarized.

Application Areas of Artificial Intelligence in Educational Administration

Artificial intelligence plays a significant role in the education sector, both in terms of administrative processes and in improving academic success and student monitoring. The application areas of this technology, which has rapidly entered our lives, in the field of education can be examined under the following headings:

Administrative Efficiency and Automation

Artificial intelligence-based automation systems improve tasks such as budget expenditures, student registrations, course schedule preparation, and efficient use of resources, thereby reducing costs and speeding up processes. In particular, the automatic design of course schedules with small data entries ensures efficient use of resources, while allowing administrators to save time and complete processes very quickly (Yılmaz, 2025). In his research on school administrators' views on artificial intelligence, Yiğittekin (2025) states that school principals find their routine administrative tasks easier and their workloads reduced thanks to artificial intelligence. As a result, school principals indicate that they save time. Administrators also anticipate that tracking complex tasks and processes, such as constantly evolving legislation and student affairs, can be conducted more systematically through the active and collaborative use of artificial intelligence systems.

Personalized Design of Learning Processes

AI-powered smart lesson designs and personalized learning platforms aim to provide educational environments tailored to each student's individual learning pace. They also facilitate increased student success by identifying student deficiencies and offering customized content according to their needs (Igbokwe, 2023; Jose, 2025).

Decision Support and Predictive Analytics

This area is largely related to data mining. With the support of predictive analytics based on AI-powered data, students with low academic achievement and a high probability of dropping out can be identified early in schools. This allows for timely interventions with AI support, providing meaningful guidance and support to the student (Igbokwe, 2023). AI-powered data-driven decision support systems enable school administrators to implement a more complex and faster process when making strategic decisions (Altuntaş, 2025).

Student Tracking and Coordination

Parents, in particular, want to be informed about their children's education and learning process. Natural language processing (NLP) and chatbot technology enable 24/7 information flow to students, teachers, and parents. This allows for stronger internal communication and student monitoring (Igbokwe, 2023). AI applications allow for continuous monitoring of student performance and academic status, enabling the creation of individualized learning plans tailored to each student (Polat, 2024).

School Administrators' and Teachers' Views on Artificial Intelligence

Every technological advancement, as is well known, brings with it both opportunities and risks. This is also true for the use of technology and artificial intelligence tools in education. As school administrators are responsible for children who are in a sensitive developmental stage and a critical age group, they must be particularly mindful of these risks. This presents a challenging situation. This challenge leaves us grappling with questions about how to effectively integrate the growing use of artificial intelligence into the school education system (Sincar, 2023).

It is essential to seek the opinions and suggestions of educators in any initiative related to education. There is as yet no widespread example of an education system without teachers. Consequently, an educational model that does not incorporate teachers' perspectives has a very low likelihood of success. For this reason, many national and international studies tend to focus on research related to digitalization in education and the use of artificial intelligence in education. Research in this field based on scientific data is becoming increasingly important with each passing day. In a study conducted by Şimşek (2025), it was observed that most teachers expressed the view that digitalization does not diminish the importance of schools and face-to-face education. However, there are also a significant number of educators who express support for traditional educational approaches. Nevertheless, the vast majority of participants indicated that they hold positive attitudes toward the digitalization of education and the use of digital technologies in education, and they view this development as beneficial.

In field studies conducted, the prevailing sentiment among educators and education stakeholders regarding artificial intelligence is generally that it represents an opportunity. Both teachers and administrators see artificial intelligence not as a threat to their professions, but rather as a helpful assistant that improves teaching processes (Dülger, 2023). However, educators frequently request technical support related to digitalization in education. Administrators, in particular, state that they need technical support to use artificial intelligence more effectively and efficiently. It is thought that this need can be met through in-service training and that a more qualified operation can be achieved (Yiğittekin, 2025). Educators generally do not consider themselves sufficiently competent in this area.

Teachers, in particular, emphasize that artificial intelligence positively affects student motivation, student monitoring, and students' academic success. Teachers view the integration of artificial intelligence into education as a way to enrich learning materials. (Bayraktar, 2023). A study conducted by Canpolat (2021) indicated that implementing student-focused guidance and psychological support programs with the aid of artificial intelligence is beneficial. It was noted that this approach would reduce the workload and enable reaching a larger number of students. It would also be beneficial in terms of time management. However, the study emphasizes that artificial intelligence cannot replace PDR specialists or perform the exact same tasks they do. The study concludes that PDR specialists believe artificial intelligence cannot provide the full range of services they offer.

Technological developments are becoming an integral part of the education sector, just as they are in every other field. Technology, which contributes to the faster and more systematic execution of tasks and processes, is leading managers to replace manual processes with smart systems. These smart systems can become managers' assistants by integrating into daily life. School principals note that artificial intelligence can assist both in task management and in teaching students' difficult topics and concepts (Dülger, 2023).

With developing technology, leaders must establish a relationship with AI tools based on strategic partnership. Rather than replacing the leader, AI is positioned as an assistant that frees them from routine tasks. This allows leaders to focus more on seeking innovations and developing high-level strategic skills. In this process, leaders also assume a role that has a transformative impact within the organization. The way a leader uses AI directly influences employees' adaptation to this technology. In fact, the leader acts as a bridge between the technology

and the employees. Future leaders are in a pioneering position that balances technical skills—such as data analysis—with advanced social skills like emotional intelligence and ethical judgment. In this sense, next-generation leadership also serves as a form of cultural architecture. Future leaders are viewed as behavioural engineers who use artificial intelligence to transform educational institutions from rigid hierarchies into more flexible, transparent, and continuously learning structures (Subrahmanyam, 2025).

Technology is a world of opportunities. With the growing prevalence of online education enabled by information technology, positive steps can be taken toward ensuring equal opportunities and access to education. Online education can deliver higher-quality educational programs to disadvantaged individuals and groups, and even to remote villages and towns. The elimination of barriers such as time and location in education can create significant opportunities for quality education.

Advantages and Disadvantages of Artificial Intelligence

Every development in the field of technology has brought with it both advantages and disadvantages. For example, while technological facilities ensure certain positive quality standards in food safety, artificial foods produced with developing technology can negatively affect human health. The development of artificial intelligence can also be seen as a development that contains both advantages and disadvantages.

Traditionally, administrators have made decisions based on their experience and intuition. Today, AI-powered systems provide objective analyses based on real-time data. This leads to greater transparency in management processes and a reduction in the margin of error. As a result, performance measurement becomes more consistent. Thanks to digital transformation, school administrators are able to monitor teacher and student performance. AI-powered systems can identify shortcomings in teaching processes and provide strategic feedback to administrators. This enables better tracking of academic performance levels and the development of improvement strategies. Additionally, AI-powered smart systems enable professional control over the use of financial resources. This allows schools to continuously monitor quality standards and dynamically revise their development plans (Altuntaş, 2025).

Igbokwe (2023) summarizes the advantages of using AI in educational management as follows: Administrative efficiency is one of the most significant benefits of artificial intelligence. AI automates routine processes in schools, allowing administrators to dedicate more time to strategic planning. Data-driven decision-making is another positive aspect. Problems can be identified before they occur, and timely intervention strategies can be developed. Personalized educational management is another advantage of AI. Analysis of student data and performance allows for the creation of solutions tailored to the needs of each individual. 24/7 uninterrupted support is also one of the advantages of artificial intelligence in educational management. AI-based chatbots strengthen the communication link by providing instant and uninterrupted feedback to students and parents. Artificial intelligence will also make a significant contribution to increasing efficiency in education by enabling faster access to information. It is believed that artificial intelligence can support the teaching process by saving time in education and educational administration (Dülger, 2023). Artificial intelligence tools offer another advantage: creating learning environments that capture students' interest. As is well known, every student has different interests and needs. Artificial intelligence also offers positive opportunities in identifying these individual interests and needs. Educational institutions can thus easily identify each student's strengths and weaknesses, interests and needs, as well as the unique positive and negative aspects of each class. This allows teachers to provide students with useful feedback, and administrators to provide teachers with useful feedback (Sincar, 2023).

While positive views on artificial intelligence predominate, there are also those who are sceptical or express negative views. One of the main negative opinions is that artificial intelligence could pose a threat to our ability to think. There are concerns that artificial intelligence may lead to a decline in cognitive development and a stagnation of thinking skills (Yiğittekin, 2025). There is also concern that artificial intelligence will make people lazy. Additionally, there are also reservations about artificial intelligence. Abstain opinions tend to focus on whether artificial intelligence can be beneficial or harmful, depending on its intended purpose and how it is used. The disadvantages and negative aspects of AI use are summarized in the study by Jose (2025) as follows: One of them is data privacy or security. The massive amount of student/parent data and personal information collected in the system can make it a target for cyberattacks and data breaches. Another topic is algorithmic bias. AI

systems can lead to unfair negative evaluations for certain student groups through erroneous data analysis. One of the disadvantages of artificial intelligence is the risk of dehumanization. Human relations and communication are very important in educational processes. This human bond between teacher-student and administrator-teacher can be damaged by the excessive use of artificial intelligence. Ethics and transparency are also among the topics that have drawn criticism regarding artificial intelligence. Uncertainties in the data collection and processing process can lead to serious security problems.

The weakest aspect of artificial intelligence in terms of education and management is its inability to develop a sense of “empathy.” This weakness can be cited as the area where teachers and administrators have an advantage over artificial intelligence. Emotional deficiency hinders the ability to perceive individuals’ diverse aspects and impedes communication. Empathy, collaboration, and emotional depth can be viewed as areas that artificial intelligence must develop on its own (Dülger, 2023).

Data Privacy, Security, and Ethical Concerns

The integration of artificial intelligence into educational platforms also brings serious risks regarding the protection of sensitive student data and information about individuals' private lives (Jose, 2025). Educational platforms can become targets of data breaches and cyberattacks because they process enormous amounts of data, including student information, student records, academic performance, and personal information belonging to students and their families. Maintaining this data with strong security measures, protecting it against unauthorized access with end-to-end encryption and security protocols, is vital. In the digital age, people are constantly online and in communication. Therefore, protecting the ever-increasing amount of data every day is emerging as a national security issue for societies. Data security should be prioritized against data breaches, and establishing an ethical framework with national digital education software will be beneficial for digitalized education (Şimşek, 2025).

While AI offers wonderful opportunities and conveniences in the field of education, it also contains serious ethical and security warnings in academic literature (Altuntaş, 2025; Polat and Hakan, 2025). The inadequacy of user consent mechanisms and the lack of clarity regarding the purpose and function of data collection applications stand out as a fundamental problem. In this sense, it is recommended that relevant institutions adopt a minimal data policy and only process necessary information as data into the system. Protecting sensitive student data is one of the top priorities that AI-supported platforms should pay attention to. To ensure data security, laws should be regulated as a matter of national security, full compliance with the prepared legal regulations should be ensured, and third-party service providers should undergo strict security audits by the relevant authorities (Jose, 2025).

Policy makers should focus on understanding both the technical aspects of technology and its social and economic impacts, while also taking into account sectoral balances within the framework of ethical principles. Most current national strategies view education solely as a tool for training AI specialists or preparing the workforce for AI. To integrate AI into education more effectively, policymakers must expand their current approaches and prioritize long-term societal benefits. To improve this process, policymakers may consider adopting the following five core principles: beneficence, autonomy, non-maleficence, explainability, and fairness (Schiff, 2022).

Conclusion and Recommendations

Historically, technology, a leading factor in making tasks more practical, is increasingly diminishing the influence of the human factor and bringing smarter systems to the forefront. These smart systems, integrated into daily life, can both eliminate humans and act as their assistants (Dülger, 2023). Along with this benefit, technological change has sometimes been one of the main causes of inequality in labour markets. Looking at the last few centuries, developments in the field of technology have generally disproportionately benefited highly educated workers. In fact, it has caused the gap between employment and income to widen even further (Cruces and Friends, 2026). With the advent of smart automation, machines have begun to replace human labour. This technological advancement initially sparked pessimism about the future of workers in society. However, as new

job opportunities emerged and it became clear that machines cannot completely replace humans, these concerns have subsided (Sincar, 2024).

Technological developments are used for various purposes in education, as in all other fields. While artificial intelligence (AI) in educational management has the potential to operate the institutional structure more systematically and effectively, it is a tool that needs to be carefully managed from ethical and security perspectives. The future and function of artificial intelligence in educational management are seen as quite bright. However, this process needs to be carried out with a human-centred balance. AI should be positioned not as a replacement for educators, but as an assistant that facilitates, supports, and improves their work (Igbokwe, 2023; Jose, 2025, Yılmaz, 2025). In fact, the use of technology has been a part of our lives for a long time. While technological advancements have largely replaced physical abilities, artificial intelligence has now become a field that also replaces cognitive abilities (Özer, 2025). Artificial intelligence is not merely a technological tool that replaces human physical abilities. Within the framework of organizational behaviour theory, artificial intelligence is also a tool that enhances individuals' leadership and cognitive abilities (Rasheed, 2025).

Artificial intelligence should be a tool that supports the human factor in educational management, rather than replacing it. Educational administrators should assume responsibility for managing technological developments within an ethical framework that is human-centred and considers human values (Altuntaş, 2025). For sustainable integration, emphasis should be placed on ethics-based policies, data management processes should be made transparent, and the digital competencies of all stakeholders should be strengthened (Varol, 2025). In conclusion, although artificial intelligence has the capacity for revolution and change in the field of educational management, the implementation of this technology requires ethical responsibility, transparent policies, and serious measures for data security (Igbokwe, 2023; Jose, 2025).

For the integration of artificial intelligence into educational management, it is necessary to state that school leaders also need to renew themselves in areas such as digital literacy, data-driven business, openness to change, and ethical awareness (Altuntaş, 2025). Almost every transaction in educational institutions is recorded, and this task is mostly performed by school principals or vice-principals. This process is quite time-consuming. In this case, school administrators are overwhelmed by paperwork instead of developing and improving school strategies. The intensity of paperwork can be said to form the basis of school principals' positive views towards artificial intelligence. There are school administrators who believe that artificial intelligence will also be beneficial in the measurement and evaluation process, which is the stage of determining student levels (Dülger, 2023). In addition, training students to evaluate AI-generated content with a critical perspective and to verify it by comparing it with reliable sources will also be among the tasks or differentiating qualities of future educators (Sui and Chang, 2026).

It is clear that artificial intelligence technology will be more integrated into the field of education and educational management in the near future. AI-powered applications will cause a significant transformation in many areas, such as facilitating faster workflows, eliminating the burden of paperwork, and creating personalized teaching platforms. With this in mind, education policymakers should establish dedicated units within their organizations to provide technical support and consultancy services (Kurt, 2024).

In general, it can be said that education policies are not yet fully compliant with artificial intelligence systems. The lack of adequate AI-related legislation, the absence of data security policies, and the varying technological infrastructures of schools make it difficult to establish a comprehensive AI strategy in the field of education management (Altuntaş, 2025). As is well known, artificial intelligence in education has a significant impact not only from a technological perspective but also in terms of pedagogy, ethics, and teacher competencies. For this reason, it is essential to take ethical principles, guidelines, and policies into account in the development and implementation of AI Technologies (Temur, 2025). It should not be overlooked that for the healthy integration of AI in education and educational administration, both technical preparation and the enhancement of educators' digital competencies, as well as the urgent preparation of an ethical, pedagogical, and managerial policy draft, are necessary.

The policy regulations that need to be implemented in the field of artificial intelligence in education management can be grouped under three headings. The first is the planning of training programs for administrators and teachers on AI literacy and usage. Compulsory training modules addressing the ethical dimensions of AI in

education should be developed for teacher candidates and current educators. The second is the strengthening of ethical principles and implementation mechanisms for AI in the education sector, and the third is the development of policies that promote inclusivity and equal opportunity. Additionally, pedagogical models that support teacher-student interaction have been developed in recent years. In this process, it is necessary to establish binding regulations with enforcement power regarding data security for all stakeholders (Özenç, 2025; Temur, 2025). In conclusion, A multi-layered ethical approach is necessary for the fair, transparent, reliable, and human-centred use of AI in education.

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